

QUIZ**LAST NAME: WADADA****FIRST NAME: DANIEL****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied /UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author /did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ

- 1. What is the first step when writing an essay?**
 - Conducting research.
 - Understanding the question.¹**
 - Developing a point of view/argument/thesis point of opinion with which to respond to the question.
 - Writing the argument starting with a good introduction.
- 2. Technology has been very useful to mankind in the aspect of learning and research development. But what disadvantage does technology have?**
 - Storing and retrieving information.
 - Writing highly accurate articles using sophisticated editing tools.
 - Carrying out research.

¹ Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Course pack Period 1*. (Euclid University Press, 2019), 3.

- Synthesising all parts of an essay into a flowing, logical finished product.²**
3. **What does effective writing require?**
- Good ideas, clear organisation, and effective word choice.³**
- Good ideas, lengthy essays, and effective word choice.
- Clear organization, effective word choice, and brief essays.
- Effective word choice, clichés, and good ideas.
4. **From where can a writer get inspiration when writing?**
- Prior experience.
- Reading books.
- Interviewing sources.
- All of the above.⁴**
5. **When researching, a writer should ...,**
- Gather facts.
- Search for sources.
- Show relevance.
- Look for facts that contradict their views.
- All of the above.⁵**
6. **What is the most commonly used tense in academic writing?**
- Past tense.
- Present Simple Tense.⁶**

² Sabranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper and Vern Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning* (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 3.

³ Ibid., 19.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations* 8th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 14.

⁵ Ibid., 25,30.

⁶ Scribbr, *Verb Tenses in Academic Writing* (scribbr.com. Last Modified 22nd September 2014. <https://www.scribbr.com/language-rules/tenses/>).

- Present tense.
 - Future tense.
7. **Why can grammar checkers fail to do?**
- Flag misspelled words.
 - Flag style mistakes.
 - Accurately provide the context within which a word has been used.**⁷
 - Suggest context-specific corrections.
8. **When is an advantage of in-house writing styles?**
- Enhance an organisation's corporate image.**⁸
 - Increased productivity.
 - Increased sales.
 - Reduction in costs.
9. **When should abbreviations used in an essay be defined?**
- The first time they are used.**⁹
 - At the end of the essay.
 - In the middle of the essay.
 - At the beginning of the essay.
10. **How are delegates seated during international conferences such as the United Nations General Assembly?**
- Randomly.
 - According to when their countries attained independence.
 - According to the respective continents.

⁷ The Writing Center, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. *Verb Tenses* (Writingcenter.unc.edu). <https://writingcenter.unc.edu/tips-and-tools/verb-tenses/>.

⁸ World Health Organisation, *WHO Style Guide*. (Geneva, World Health Education, 2004), 2.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 3.

- According to the English language alphabetical name order of their countries.¹⁰

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¹⁰ Op.cit., World Health Organisation, 5